

Research Article

Present Status of the Level of Agricultural Mechanization available for Cassava Processing Operations in Ogun State of Nigeria

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Abstract

Cassava is seen as a very strong food security crop in Nigeria. The processing of cassava through the use of cassava processing machines needs to be encouraged among cassava processors in order to boost cassava processing operations in Nigeria. A lot of foreign exchange could be earned through the export of cassava products. A National Mechanization survey exercise was carried out in April 2018 by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin in Ogun State to investigate the present level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey exercise in the State. Survey results revealed for the nine (9) cassava processing operations involved showed that cassava washing operation was 100% manually done in all the cassava processing units visited in the State. A total of 58.19% was recorded for manual processing method for the nine (9) processing operations involved for cassava. It was also noted that a total of 31.39% was recorded for mechanical processing method for the seven (7) cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering, drying and milling operations contributed to this figure. A lot needs to be done by the Ogun State government in supporting cassava processors in the area of increasing the number of cassava processing machines needed for boosting cassava processing operations in the State.

Keywords: cassava, processing, manually, mechanical, operation, grating.

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Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is a root and tuber crop that has been identified as important for food security, especially in Africa and serves as a staple food for over 200 million people in the African continent (CTA, 2005). Cassava has become the magic crop in Nigeria as a result of the Presidential initiative on cassava some years ago with good export potential (Iyagba and Anyanwu, 2012). In Africa, cassava is beginning to be used in partial substitution for wheat flour (Ojekunle, 2010).

Nigeria is the world's largest producer of cassava, Thailand is the largest exporting country of dried cassava and in the subtropical region of Southern China, and cassava is the fifth largest crop produced. Cassava is the third largest source of food carbohydrate in the tropics and also an important source of food which gives the highest yield of food energy per cultivated area per day among crop plant except possibly for sugarcane. Cassava plays a particularly important role in agriculture especially in developing countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, because it does well on poor soils and with low rainfall, and because it is a perennial crop that can be harvested as required (Onyenwoke and Simonyan, 2014). According to Akerele *et al.* (2018), cassava has the following economic importance in the Nigerian economy.

1. Source of employment to millions of people both in its production and processing.
2. Source of income to individuals and serves as revenue for the government.
3. Cassava serves as a source of foreign exchange to individuals and the government.
4. Cassava serves as raw materials for some industries.
5. Cassava is a rich and very important source of food item to millions of people.

Nigerians prefer cassava compared to any other staple food because of its availability all year round and consequently, cassava has a broad base of end users (IITA, 2006) as a cash crop, cassava generates cash incomes for the largest number of households in comparison to other staples. Cassava is good for consumption when properly processed and prepared. Cassava contains significant amounts of calcium (500 mg/100g), phosphorus (400 mg/100g), and vitamin C (25 mg/100g). Cassava consists of 15% peel and 85% fresh tuber flesh. The tuber consists of 20 - 30% starch, 62% water content, 2% protein, 1 - 2% fiber with trace of vitamin and minerals (FAO, 2001).

There were increased demand for processed cassava products such as chips/chunks, flour, gari, starch and others. Nigeria was recognized as one of the leading producers of cassava in the world, since 2002 (FAO, 2004). Considering the importance of cassava to the Nigerian economy, it became necessary for the Nigerian government to promote the export of cassava products as a means of generating foreign exchange for the nation. Therefore, this study aims at investigating the present status of the level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations in Ogun State of Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ogun State. The State has a total of 20 Local Government Areas. According to Oloruntoba and Adegbite (2006), Ogun State is located in the southwestern part of Nigeria. It covers 16,762 km². The State borders Lagos State to the south, Oyo and Osun states to the North, Ondo State to the east and the Republic of Benin to the west.

Agriculture which is the economic mainstay of Ogun, produces rice, corn (maize), cassava (manioc), yams, plantains, and bananas. Cocoa, kola nuts, rubber, palm oil and palm kernels, tobacco, cotton, and timber are the main cash crops (<https://www.britannica.com/place/Ogun-state-Nigeria>).

Research Methodology

The study involves the use of primary source of data to obtain relevant information needed for this study. The structured questionnaires used for this study was designed by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin. The structured questionnaire was used to embark on a National Mechanization survey exercise in Ogun State. The survey was carried out in April 2018 using competent and experienced staff of the Ogun State Agricultural Development Programme office that are familiar with the terrain of the State. A total of 500 questionnaires were taken to Ogun State for the survey exercise by one of the key Technical staff of the Centre (NCAM) for the purpose of organizing a one day induction workshop programme for the enumerators to be used for the survey exercise. These enumerators were trained on how the structured questionnaires would be filled by the respondents. The NCAM survey questionnaires were administered in the 20 Local Government Areas of the State. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey. During the course of carrying out the survey, NCAM in their own part monitored the survey activity by

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paying personal visit to some of the target groups in the different Local Government Areas of the State as a way to ensure that information provided by the enumerators were genuine. A total of 328 questionnaires were returned back to NCAM as filled questionnaires. The returned questionnaires were thoroughly scrutinized one after the other by the same Technical staff so as to ensure that the proper information needed from the survey carried out were properly provided for use during data capturing. After data capturing, the questionnaires were sorted out by separating those into agro-processing occupation from other occupations contained in the structured questionnaire. A total of 153 agro-processors were found in Ogun State as 80 of these agro-processors were noticed to fall into cassava processing operations. The 80 questionnaires meant for those into cassava processing operations were specifically used for this study.

Statistical Tool

Data obtained from the 80 respondents into cassava processing operations in Ogun State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation.

Results and Discussion

The summary of the data computed for the agro-processors into cassava processing operations in Ogun State is presented in Table 1. It is good to note from Table 1, that a total of 153 agro-processing units were visited in the State out of which 80 agro-processing units representing 52.29% were into cassava processing operations. It can be deduced from Table 1, that there are 9 cassava processing operations captured in the structured questionnaires designed by NCAM for use in the National Mechanization survey exercise carried out in Ogun State. Arranging the outcome of those that picked manual processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, results obtained revealed that we have a total of 80 representing 100% of the cassava processing units visited adopt manual processing method for washing of cassava. A total of 73 representing 91.25% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of chipping cassava. A total of 65 representing 81.25% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of bagging cassava. A total of 54 representing 67.50% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of peeling and garification of cassava, respectively. A total of 30 representing 37.50% of the cassava processing units visited

engage in the manual processing method of drying cassava. A total of 26 representing 32.50% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of grating cassava. A total of 19 representing 23.75% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of dewatering cassava mash. A total of 18 representing 22.50% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of milling cassava. A total of 58.19% was recorded for manual processing method for the nine processing operations involved for cassava.

Table 1. Results of Level of Agricultural Mechanization obtained for Cassava Processing operations in Ogun State

Processing operations	Level of Agricultural Mechanization					
	MN		MC		UD	
	A	B (%)	A	B (%)	A	B (%)
Peeling	54	67.50	Nil	Nil	26	32.50
Washing	80	100	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Grating	26	32.50	53	66.25	1	1.25
Chipping	73	91.25	7	8.75	Nil	Nil
Dewatering	19	23.75	60	75.00	1	1.25
Drying	30	37.50	46	57.50	4	5
Garification	54	67.50	9	11.25	17	21.25
Milling	18	22.50	46	57.50	16	20
Bagging	65	81.25	5	6.25	10	12.50
Total	419	N/A	226	N/A	75	N/A
	(58.19%)		(31.39%)		(10.42%)	

Keynote: A = Frequency count; B = Frequency count in its percentage value; MN = Manual operation; MC = Mechanical operation; UD = Undecided; N/A = Not applicable

Note: Total No. into agro-processing activity in Ogun State = 153; Total No. of agro-processors into cassava processing operation = 80; Percentage of agro-processors into cassava processing = 52.29%

Likewise, arranging the outcome of those that picked mechanical processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, we have a total of 60 representing 75% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for dewatering cassava mash. A total of 53 representing 66.25% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of grating cassava. A total of 46 representing 57.50% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of drying and milling of cassava, respectively. A total of 9 representing 11.25% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for the garification of cassava. A total of seven representing 8.75% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for chipping cassava. A total of 5 representing 6.25% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for bagging cassava. A total of 31.39% was recorded for mechanical processing methods for the seven cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering, drying and milling of cassava contributed to this figure.

It can be seen from the analysis carried out as shown in Table 1, that washing operation of cassava is manually done in all the cassava processing units visited in Ogun State. The adoption of mechanized cassava operations can only be highly seen in the areas of dewatering (75%), grating (66.25%), drying (57.50%) and milling (57.50%) operations. Data captured for those cassava processing units visited that picked undecided for their unit operation was not considered for discussion in this study as all discussion were based on those that choose between manual and mechanical means of processing cassava. For record purpose, a total of 10.42% was recorded for those that picked undecided in 7 of their unit operations as presented in Table 1.

Conclusion

In Ogun State of Nigeria, a National Mechanization survey exercise was carried out in April 2018 by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization in order to determine the present status of the level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations in the State. Investigation revealed that all the cassava processing units visited in the State adopt manual processing method for washing of cassava. It was also noted that 75% and 66.25% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for dewatering and grating of cassava, respectively. In addition to this, 57.50% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for both drying and milling of cassava. Cassava is seen as a strong

food security crop in Nigeria and for this reason its processing operation needs to be encouraged in order to boost cassava processing operation in Ogun State. Much needs to be done by the State government in ensuring the level of agricultural mechanization for cassava processing operations is increased to make Ogun State food sufficiency in the area of providing the various finished products of cassava for the teeming population of the people living in the state.

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